

Digitalization of Trucking System A Future in Supply Chains

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Abstract

Logistic, Supply chain considered being the largest road network across the various spheres, covering approximately 65 per cent of cargo movement by road, railways, sea, within the various circles in supply chain. During the past three decades of movement of goods by road, railways, sea, is getting considerable very high, in volume, weight, also with digitalization given importance, for momentous journey within the supply chain, while growth on the praise is never being expected as in the demand for the years to come, but with growing demand in digitalization, with the way as of coming on the demand is in a big way trucking system in supply chain. Having trucking industry in the field of supply chain, among the various spheres, have remained the most unorganized, also among the other features compared among the other modes of transportation. Pointing out to digitization's exploration, there might be big bliss for any organization to explore the possibilities for digitization on the trucking features that will transfer the logistic value chain within the organization in supply chain.

Simple application with the help of technology, also the re-thinking on the various of trucking on the fundamentals is like a simple methods of trucking methods to be adopted, with a combination of an ever changing technology in the trucking infrastructure, will be moved down by the guided of wealth of information to be shared, from transportation, autonomous driving, electrifying, also digital automation connectivity, which enables the advent of smart logistics in trucking industry, while on lowering the operating cost, infrastructure maintenance, increasing the efficiency, also of boosting the safety with the use, advent of artificial intelligence in supply chain. The largest or the biggest concept of digitalization in trucking industry from the economic point, will be the ability to communicate with the fleet management, using the Radio Frequency Identification system, Global Positioning System, with shipping of goods to the customer ultimately to consumers for consumption in supply chain. Future of trucking industry digitalization will be on cloud-based solution, for better freight forwarding techniques matching with truckers, which will be eventually, contented to be able to determine whether they can accommodate additional freight in consideration with supply chain. With the use of truck trailer, as an option for carrying additional freight, the

trucking industry will be able to determine its available space, also the required weight, volume, accordingly as per the schedule route map available in supply chain.

Digitalization in supply chain will continue in trucking industry, become more integrated, collaborative, with different parts of supply chain, working together closely managing traffic management, with telecommunication network, on the same day, or next day delivery, with more other relevant information on using sensors, to communicate the relevant data, on to the digital freight platform, matching to any performance on any additional load, so as to not suffer any reversal logistic platforms for a quick delivery in supply chain.

Keywords: Digitalization, Trucking, Infrastructure maintenance, Technology, Collaborative, Shipping, Freight.

1. Introduction

The next step in digitalization of trucking industry system is to immediately being concurrence on the next step, to bring the benefit of advancement of the logistic sector, to today's virtue of the improvement in the overall customer experience's, it is the service, also driving the excellence in the operation of trucking system in supply chain. Digitization of trucking industry will help to evaluate the performance of operations of the vehicle, also on the conditions of the performance of the manning on the condition of the vehicle, with the use of best available technology, that can be performed with digitalization, as the fleet owners can link to all the available fleet, attached to the system, also effectively monitor the performance of the individual fleet by the use of digitalization as a technology in supply chain. With the use of high level of the contained data, also on the basis of the efficient network relying upon the support system for managing, with the optimization of the trucking transport operations, using the many of the digital technologies, within the processing level, also having the full integration of connected to truck industry, for real-time logistics, within the basis of smart data across the entire supply chain with deep learning, in order to amplify the procedure from spares parts, to material supply from manufactures to warehouse distributors ending with the final consumer in supply chain.

The logistic industry is one of the rapidly growing sectors, which has been transpiring the aspiration of trucking digitalization, for the convenience of the several players in trucking organization, working to organize on the previous of the unorganized sector in supply chain. Technology has been a major factor on influencing, within the development of service providers, that have been deployed on the cloud-based solution, having the purpose of internal, also combined with external oriented business process operations, on truck sourcing, releasing orders, electronic e-payment, real time visibility of truck tracking positioning, sharing statement of account payable, receivable, sharing of POD (proof of delivery) electronic e-invoicing, are others referred to as digitalization in logistic, as service providers in supply chain. Among the highest interest in digitalization, is the LSP's (layered service provider-interception, is also on the modification of inbound and outbound internet traffic.) is on account of the promise, it can hold of the delivery on the basis of over a time bound, in increasing the efficiency of the overall eco-system, as well as on each of the participants of the eco-system, which includes the consignor, the service provider, also among themselves considered as the fleet owner who are also considered as the providers of suppliers, vendors, service entities among the organization in supply chain.

Emerging technology focused are revolutionizing the way organization, are functioning on the leveraged technology, to offer seamless trucking digitalization on a transparent, also on an efficient operations with strict adherence to limitless, travel in supply chain.

2. Purpose of the Study

Artificial intelligence, data analytics, also combined with Internet of Things based on the perfect technologies that are liable to make it easier for digitalization among the trucking system, to keep track on the deliveries while making fleet management operation much easier in supply chain. Logistic, supply chain has also helped organization to control the hours required for periodic service on the deployment of manpower, plan optimized by efficient travel routes, while facilitating security operations through 24x7 surveillance in supply chain. Fuel sensing sensors, geo-fueling to manage, auto ignition cut off, retinal sensor; (cells in eye that sense light) digital locks (smart lock, e-lock) have completely transformed the way the section have been functioning over the years driving to recruitment of technological talent as well as skill based resources in the organization based on supply chain.

Powered by massive amount of real-time big data, sophisticated machine leaning algorithm, also lighting fast processing in digitalized supply chain, with the seeing of real time predictive analysis, optimized with cognitive supply chain, that is likely to transform the way organization operate in much the same way that autonomous vehicles will define how digital truck operate, as this has been a part of supply chain which is driving extraordinary results bring innovative ideas to the organization in supply chain.

It has been suggested that the logistic value chain considered within the country, will be able to adhere to the best transportation solution, such as the availability of the right vehicle selection, route, or planning efficient delivery, considering real-time tracking, reliable documentation, with a control reduced transit time, for goods transported from the point of origin to that of consumption on a real-time basis, with the aid of the significant growth played in the process on the instances of supply chain.

3. Literature Review

Mass manufacturing with the consent of the suppliers are being considered to be the movement of goods, also giving attention to smoother, faster deliveries improved operation management, which are being introduced as more productive. The major trend is for the lookout for the development of digitalization of trucking operations, also tracking the route optimization, the tracing of goods within the movement, fleet performance movement management, preventive maintenance, maintenances spares inventory, focus on improving better drive on the life of network system, within the organization using 80% of the block chain amalgamations technique in supply chain.

On the improvement in logistic, supply chain with more than a decade on the Global Positioning System, as this was considered to be luxury to the trucking digitalization program, on the truck tracking system, but now it has become mandatory fitting, in most of the digitalized trucks plying in supply chain. The digitalization system in trucking will completely transform in the near future, which will eventually be that trucks that will drive themselves, bringing digitalization on the utilization of manpower requirement, giving a free hand to trucking organization, so as to enable on to take on utilization of an administrative data, which may become an essential part in doing away within the reach of supply chain. As these advances will have an equally profound growth on the trucking industry, the effect on the entire logistic supply system in trucking, with the arrival of shipments from factory warehouses, to the end –customer on a timely basis will precisely be given priority to the truck industry across the supply chain, which is likely to fall under the transparency, into the whereabouts of the goods, also ultimately bringing digitalization in trucking industry for better performance, that will be able to communicate the contents, also on the destination, with other trends, options, which add on to the available technology, within the platform of network, that will automatically match shipment records with trucks, on the available space, of 75% in order to re-route them to the necessary destination in supply chain.

4. Research Methodology: Primary/Secondary

Primary: As researched it was found that trucking industry used to be considered as the last dark content, (unstructured or untapped data that is collected used or analyzed to extract value) among the logistic, supply value chain, which have been difficult to conquer due to the various factors in the concept that were available with digitalization technology, since the transformation in trucking industry have begun in supply chain. Numerous trucking industry in logistic, supply chain, within the country having wide spread market, are investing in to the Research and Development of the digital platform, also trying to offer innovative solutions to transform the eco-system. Having come to the use of Global Positioning System, devices to track the vehicle have become an increasingly an adopted norm, with organized fleet operators. GPS (global position system) itself on having a transformative effect by reducing the bottleneck, in order to save the trucking industry on the time spent on various aspects, with the concept of lot-of-work that is happening on the route optimization, introduction of block chain technology, on the conditions of fleet management, essential on the vehicle performance management to drive the condition of change, also bring in the concept of complete transformation to the future of trucking industry system in supply chain..

Secondary: At a fundamental part, of the research the cloud-based solution provides information flow well within the cross section of the trucking industry in the organization, which includes the controversial part between suppliers, also with buyers on the different products of service. Any transaction between the two players of the eco-system does get the facilities with speed, also on the need for an error free communication including 1. **Finding the customer service provider in a supply chain.** 2. **Proper shipping documents preparation.** 3. **Status of delivery, also with proper invoicing in trucking industry.** 4. **Payments made or received.** 5. **Statements of transaction, also giving priority to accounts, reconciliation in trucking industry.** The main goal in trucking industry is to organize traffic flow, automate routing system, with digitalization, improve parking facilities, and also consider efficient safety measures, in order to allow proper man-power utilization in supply chain. On the technological changes that will provide drive with real-time information about the congestion, also take care of accidents, will also automate digitalization on the update of routes in supply chain. Automation on parking facilities, features will provide suggestions on where to park, how to park, will depend on the driving level, the fatigue assumption, no-entry timings, also take care of the traffic situation. The future of driving travel on the country's positioning shall be an integration of advanced driving technology, such as adapting cruise control, free from collision, avoidance such as moving down the road in tight convoys close enough to benefit from decrease in aerodynamic drag in supply chain. Logistic, supply would conclude to surely increase efficiency, with the introduction of new sensor connectivity

technologies, limiting the truck to its surrounding, giving prominence to repair maintenance on single highway, also in the longer run as they will lead to the brave utilization of logistic, on the basis of autonomous digital trucking system in supply chain.

5. Results

Analysis: With Logistic, supply chain organizations having neglected digitalization in various organizations, so the appeal by the National Logistic Policy, that Digitalization will not only bring in efficiency, but content, as well, as the opportunity in question, remains for the truck trucking industry to accept these changes. Major manufacturing organization, also distributors, Third Party Logistics, are already looking into the investment in new technology as part of the digitalization agenda, and this will increasingly become important soon after optimization, on the operations, that will enable the customers to improve their business performances in supply chain. Over the next few users in trucking industry on digitalization, the logistic providers in trucking industry will provide to help build transparency in service, quality, pricing, with the use technology to improve their own efficiency there by giving better capability to provide better quality of service at lower price. With the digital logistic providers, in trucking industry, growing in number, size, volume, they dominate the logistic ecosystem, and help to reduce the overall logistic cost for every buyer, manufacturer, supplier vendor in supply chain.

The whole sequence of trucking transaction, also in the process right from the instances of customer creating an order to vehicle allocation, container tracking, (from loading to unloading) advance planning for clearance, demurrage, detention, as their execution on the trip, will be analyzed, at a very minute granular level to identify optimization on opportunities in supply chain.

Truckers in trucking industry will also increasingly focus on strengthening last mile connectivity, which provide information, on digitalization on gate entry, control tower, auto dock assignment, dock utilization within the supply chain, by acquiring truckers on a smaller trucking industry, on operating with Tier II and Tier III cities, among the changes on activities in logistic, supply chain.

6. Discussions and Findings

Discussion: The fleet will be modernized substantially, with efficient trucking system digitalized, also will be equipped, fitted with sensors, control with actuators for easy traceability, being always staying connected over wired system, also the needed wireless needed equipment accessible for network in supply chain.

Among the service level improvements were long desirous with the trucking industry, customer distrust, fragmented spilt operation, a lack of adherence on to time-to-time had earned the trucking industry an uneven performance, ably with the growth of e-commerce, and a constant surge in demand for the services of encouraging many new trucking transporters to make a straight line on time for the sector, to an extent that is being considered most important in trucking industry, currently with established truckers within the domain, that are looking forward to implement technological solution to reduce operating costs, inefficiency and earn trust among the various organization in supply chain. .

Analysis: Findings: Among the Hub and Spoke distribution is considered to be a form of transportation in a trucking organization, that optimizes, in which traffic routes are digitalized with Global Positioning System, on the organized system as a series of spoke, that connect on to lying points to a central position, as a simple form of the distribution or connection, which may be contrasted in terms of scope, focus, strategic operation cost, with point to point system, in which each point has a direct route to every other point, which have a principle method of transporting products, with proper freight paid system, that is from the hub and spoke point in supply chain. .

Digitalization transformation is fast becoming a survival strategy, in the trucking system to be adopted in fleet management, or transportation, including passenger transportation, on adapting high technological solutions,

as this may be adopted to be very slow, with better innovation as trucking digitalization is the only way to move forward, in order to adapt situations so as to offer, also go ahead in supply chain.

7. Future Work/Conclusions/Recommendations

Future Work: Digitalization of trucking system, will transform with trucking system within the organization linked with Original Equipment manufacturer logistic supply chain organizations warehouses, associated with onward or outbound delivery business will necessarily need to compensate with rising prices of fuel, in order to come to a conclusion, by having better focus on the needs of trained manpower, in order to adapt better practices, reduction in fuel costs, avoid speeding of vehicles, in order bring in increase in profits in supply chain. Predictive analysis in trucking industry helps to transform logistic organizations, manage, have fleet of trucks to create efficient delivery routes with better accuracy, enabling timely, make better optimal use of resources in routing in supply chain.

Recommendations: Technology in automation of trucking in logistic, supply chain, can also overcome the utilization of manpower, on manning the transportation, making it more efficient, agile, smarter, as a future proof in digitalization in the trucking industry, on the better system adopted on freight tracking, delivery management, as a future proof on digitalization, on a proper schedule with supplier's, to also elevate artificial intelligence technology on route mapping, allowing trucking system to minimize moving time, redeem fuel consumption with strictest deadlines in supply chain.

Conclusions: With Internet of Things being the foremost technology as choice as digitalization in a trucking organization, with a choice of customization in automation, using artificial intelligence, machine learning, can enable on the functioning of value chain, with skills required for manning the trucking system, with skills, communicating strategic thinking, has been considered as an important in supply chain.

Limitations: High implementation of costs in tracking in trucking industry, does have impact on digital systems, lack of standardization, data security, privacy, with increased problems, resistance to change, problems of small fleet, connectivity on infrastructure, have problems digital trucking, depending upon stable internet, regulatory, compliances challenges, maintenance spare parts, dependence on Third party logistics trucking, with limited operations in supply chain.

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